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The Food Production Index

It grew between 2013 and 2021 by an average of 10% for the analyzed countries

The Food Production Index covers food crops that are considered edible and contain nutrients. Coffee and tea are excluded because, although edible, they have no nutritional value.

Ranking of countries by value of food production in 2021. Senegal ranks first by value of the Food Production Index with a value of 177.74, followed by Qatar with a value of 162.02 units, Saudi Arabia with 158.96, Djibouti with 144.13, and Oman with 143.95. In the middle of the table are Eswatini with 105.13 units, followed by Gabon with 105.09, the Kyrgyz Republic with 104.94, Yemen with 104.92, Eritrea with 104.86, and Guatemala with 104.80. Malta closes the ranking with 76.43, East Timor with 76.34, St Lucia with 75.92, Gambia with 72.50 units, Cuba with 68.31.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change in the food production index between 2013 and 2021. Senegal ranks first by the value of the percentage change in the food production index between 2013 and 2021 with a value of 119.59, followed by Qatar with a value of 66.33 units, Malawi with 64.91, Tajikistan with a value of 63.58, and Mongolia with 59.2 units. In the middle of the table is Papua New Guinea with a value of 9.31, followed by the Central African Republic with 9.22, Jamaica with 8.9, Turkmenistan with 8.84, Gabon with 8.81, Burundi with 8.33. St Lucia closes the ranking with -23.70, Malta with -24.7, Tonga with -25.9, Cuba with -29.82, Samoa -32.6, Gambia with -33.84. Between 2013 and 2021, the value of the percentage change in food production grew on average by about 10%.

Machine learning and predictions. Below we analyze eight different machine learning algorithms used for predicting the future value of the food production index. The algorithms are classified according to the maximization of the R-squared and the reduction of statistical errors, i.e. MAE-Mean Squared Error, MSE-Mean Squared Error, Root Mean Squared Error-RMSE. The algorithms have been trained with 80% of the available data while the remaining 20% can be used for actual prediction. The ordering of the algorithms is indicated as follows:

- Polynomial Regression with a value of 4 units;
- Gradient Boosted Trees with a value of 10 units;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a value of 13 units;
- Random Forest Regression with a value of 14 units;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a value of 21 units;
- Linear Regression with a value of 22 units;
- Simple Regression Tree with a value of 28 units;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a value of 32 units.

The most advanced algorithm is the Polynomial Regression with a value of 4. By applying the Polynomial Regression algorithm, it is possible to predict the future trend of the Food Production

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Index. It is possible to distinguish winner countries, i.e. countries for which a growth in the value of the Food Production Index is predicted, and losers countries, i.e. countries for which a reduction in the value of the Food Production Index is predicted.

Winning countries. Among the winning countries there are: St. Lucia with a value of 241.86, Croatia with 166.00, The Gambia with 140.42, Tonga with 81.91, Bosnia and Herzegovina with a value of 67.98, Canada with 61.36, Maldives with 42.82, Iran with 30.32, Vanuatu with 29.35, Bahrain with 26.59, Rwanda with 25.13, North Korea with 19.96, Greece with 19.08, Paraguay with 16.62, Tunisia with 16.16, Sao Tome and Principe with 14.08, Lesotho with 11.46, Thailand with 11.08, Austria with 10.43, Micronesia with 10.21, Philippines with 9.35, Djibouti with 9.21, Belarus with 7.91, Spain with 7.59, Mozambique with 6.74, Guatemala with 6.48, Kazakhstan with 6.42, Comoros with 6.00, Yemen with 5.66, Georgia with 3.35, Grenada with 3.21, Papua New Guinea with 2.809, Sweden with 2.71, New Zealand with 1.32, Solomon Islands with 1.09, Italy with 0.96.

Losing countries. The best predictor algorithm also predicts the losers' countries, i.e., countries for which a reduction in the value of the Food Production Index is predicted. These countries are St. Kittis and Nevis with -0.68, Malaysia with -1.38, Zambia with -1.43, Russian Federation with -1.99, Chad with -4.82, United Arab Emirates with -5, 59, Uzbekistan with -7.30, Mauritania with -7.69, Bangladesh with -8.38, Ecuador with -9.87, Afghanistan with -10.08, Uganda with -11.07, Peru with -11.69, Bolivia with -12.33, Azerbaijan with -14.03, Senegal with -15.16, Pakistan with -16.91, Brunei Darussalam with -17.17, Saudi Arabia with -23.77, Qatar with -32, 85, Portugal with -39.74.

Conclusions. The value of the Food Production Index grew by an average of 10% between 2013 and 2021. The leading countries in the Food Production Index are Saudi Arabia, India, Mongolia. It should be noted that the value of the Food Production Index is calculated as a 100-based indicator. Therefore, the changes are calculated with respect to the reference period, i.e., the period 2014-2016. All countries tend to have marginal growth in the value of the Food Production Index, with some exceptions namely Myanmar, Venezuela, Iran, and Canada. Obviously, the reduction in the value of the Food Production Index may be due to political-economic reasons such as, for example, in the case of Venezuela and Iran, or for strictly economic reasons, i.e., Canada. The development of technologies in the agricultural sector should lead to an increase in the value of agricultural production and therefore to further growth in the value of the Food Production Index. It therefore follows that in the future the value of the Food Production Index should continue to grow, even with new agricultural production methods that could also support further increases in the growth of the world population.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Country Name	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Afghanistan	94,29	101,67	95,99	102,34	100,02	96,07	112,55	118,09	113,74
Albania	95,62	96,82	100,07	103,11	103,90	106,08	104,11	105,77	103,44
Algeria	98,04	96,95	100,26	102,79	102,87	108,60	112,16	112,31	104,62
Angola	110,73	97,41	100,32	102,27	103,19	105,59	107,53	112,60	114,59
Antigua and Barbuda	101,46	100,66	100,31	99,03	93,31	87,56	86,62	86,45	84,87
Argentina	94,00	95,09	103,96	100,95	106,03	97,49	112,59	109,35	108,23
Armenia	92,50	97,40	106,65	95,95	95,24	83,48	81,28	85,99	84,87
Australia	96,86	100,80	101,22	97,98	108,12	97,50	91,53	89,56	106,70
Austria	96,24	102,03	97,37	100,60	98,48	100,51	99,96	101,84	99,80
Azerbaijan	98,45	94,84	101,27	103,88	107,73	113,33	121,46	122,20	126,98
Bahamas, The	95,05	98,78	100,28	100,94	100,71	101,85	99,87	99,94	99,55
Bahrain	86,22	83,41	98,70	117,89	137,69	138,95	129,86	121,21	128,36
Bangladesh	96,33	98,72	100,48	100,80	107,85	107,75	108,34	111,48	116,39
Barbados	98,01	99,11	102,64	98,24	102,65	108,19	105,02	88,36	88,78
Belarus	96,07	101,14	100,05	98,81	103,29	99,37	101,63	106,62	103,00
Belgium	95,83	101,81	101,33	96,87	102,59	98,38	100,97	101,49	102,49
Belize	99,62	102,29	102,10	95,61	103,64	98,65	96,97	95,16	101,44
Benin	99,15	103,07	94,87	102,05	104,57	109,45	117,25	114,66	119,17

Bhutan	89,25	93,34	96,13	110,53	109,79	95,20	102,23	111,02	99,35
Bolivia	93,09	96,03	101,80	102,17	101,63	109,45	109,81	109,36	116,57
Bosnia and Herzegovina	104,99	88,85	99,16	111,99	94,61	115,08	105,35	115,05	95,54
Botswana	115,07	99,91	105,37	94,72	93,21	95,98	100,88	100,72	106,04
Brazil	97,64	99,15	101,82	99,03	107,16	107,09	109,25	111,58	112,20
Brunei Darussalam	105,53	99,41	97,15	103,44	99,96	102,11	100,29	107,52	116,68
Bulgaria	102,69	100,74	97,47	101,79	106,22	105,80	107,73	90,37	109,59
Burkina Faso	95,42	99,27	98,53	102,20	95,27	112,24	121,26	123,97	116,21
Burundi	114,19	100,92	94,86	104,22	101,08	124,44	135,10	132,41	123,70
Cabo Verde	104,85	99,38	100,81	99,81	91,79	77,86	78,90	80,66	82,01
Cambodia	99,61	98,32	98,30	103,38	107,55	111,42	110,22	112,52	115,25
Cameroon	92,38	95,55	100,39	104,06	98,81	99,71	100,86	100,72	103,47
Canada	101,00	94,65	98,53	106,82	108,54	109,32	110,39	113,34	95,95
Central African Republic	101,87	99,62	99,15	101,23	104,50	106,86	107,21	109,42	111,26
Chad	94,52	97,54	97,01	105,45	108,64	114,60	118,38	121,27	122,80
Chile	101,06	97,58	101,34	101,08	98,86	108,63	107,59	105,56	107,11
China	95,89	97,60	101,36	101,04	102,22	103,16	103,21	104,71	108,74
Colombia	96,08	96,87	100,47	102,65	96,74	101,98	104,81	103,67	105,67
Comoros	101,60	97,16	98,60	104,24	104,44	105,81	105,84	106,31	105,82
Congo, Dem. Rep.	92,78	99,38	100,02	100,59	105,61	107,82	109,93	114,61	119,58
Congo, Rep.	93,37	98,96	102,38	98,67	99,95	102,69	103,94	103,95	107,96
Costa Rica	95,89	99,32	98,93	101,75	104,93	105,65	101,84	99,51	102,66
Cote d'Ivoire	86,47	94,70	104,26	101,04	111,53	114,56	116,75	119,82	122,03
Croatia	96,35	94,22	96,61	109,17	93,45	102,18	99,50	108,66	82,14
Cuba	97,33	97,39	99,51	103,10	103,91	95,02	95,36	73,26	68,31
Cyprus	99,46	97,77	103,15	99,08	104,00	102,36	106,12	106,37	110,73
Czechia	93,00	101,45	97,07	101,48	94,95	92,93	92,95	97,33	97,70
Denmark	97,30	99,93	101,24	98,83	102,11	92,87	100,59	102,66	102,94
Djibouti	121,62	102,73	83,93	113,34	126,72	131,22	136,75	139,79	144,13
Dominica	99,04	98,59	99,04	102,37	99,64	99,44	100,26	100,50	100,12
Dominican Republic	90,69	96,67	99,72	103,61	105,65	112,98	116,56	114,28	115,77
Ecuador	94,18	101,59	103,43	94,97	96,17	97,21	100,44	99,46	104,11
Egypt, Arab Rep.	96,03	99,73	101,50	98,77	100,98	96,32	100,61	103,76	102,75
El Salvador	99,05	99,72	97,00	103,28	102,77	99,47	102,87	97,95	98,09
Equatorial Guinea	94,81	96,80	103,28	99,92	102,38	102,49	102,64	103,12	101,89
Eritrea	100,50	100,20	99,20	100,60	103,34	103,61	103,91	104,32	104,86
Estonia	92,45	97,32	111,23	91,45	99,56	84,71	106,74	107,75	98,20
Eswatini	101,73	101,58	100,19	98,23	101,53	104,10	104,02	103,02	105,13
Ethiopia	90,74	96,90	101,08	102,02	106,69	106,10	110,36	119,21	116,31
Fiji	99,95	107,57	109,42	83,01	112,77	117,90	120,46	114,48	114,98
Finland	99,50	101,04	99,53	99,43	98,01	92,95	102,16	98,55	93,54
France	96,27	102,50	102,22	95,29	101,31	97,32	98,14	92,56	96,21
Gabon	96,58	99,11	100,04	100,85	102,20	103,47	103,70	104,12	105,09
Gambia, The	109,59	97,75	107,67	94,58	82,07	63,48	69,98	73,40	72,50
Georgia	112,94	100,26	102,13	97,61	89,11	104,54	105,89	116,50	117,49
Germany	97,07	102,97	99,27	97,76	97,50	91,86	94,40	95,43	94,47
Ghana	94,94	99,15	99,82	101,03	107,84	113,12	115,75	118,31	117,93

Greece	93,64	97,20	103,65	99,15	99,76	98,37	100,63	100,36	94,99
Grenada	84,01	95,20	103,03	101,77	94,44	96,76	91,52	91,17	94,42
Guatemala	86,35	96,67	100,70	102,63	100,23	103,30	101,74	105,36	104,80
Guinea	93,00	95,75	99,95	104,31	110,36	115,04	118,71	126,52	129,80
Guinea-Bissau	100,73	95,56	100,94	103,51	105,10	107,66	112,83	117,29	121,17
Guyana	93,55	91,75	110,71	97,54	105,47	110,41	109,50	112,79	105,78
Haiti	99,88	101,93	98,86	99,21	94,12	88,97	80,52	75,92	81,77
Honduras	102,45	95,15	100,10	104,75	104,41	107,09	106,60	103,64	102,30
Hungary	88,31	100,22	95,39	104,39	98,88	100,79	99,38	96,11	92,12
Iceland	92,91	95,52	100,06	104,42	107,98	108,07	107,04	103,56	103,82
India	96,60	99,25	98,49	102,26	108,86	114,18	116,09	120,06	123,84
Indonesia	99,93	99,43	101,97	98,61	110,11	115,84	109,60	113,42	114,09
Iran, Islamic Rep.	96,85	101,31	98,50	100,18	95,42	87,04	91,76	87,13	83,78
Iraq	145,63	138,30	80,68	81,03	78,72	77,35	123,65	149,03	123,62
Ireland	89,95	96,20	100,60	103,19	110,16	110,11	114,38	115,97	118,64
Israel	96,52	100,24	99,08	100,68	101,76	99,45	100,60	102,05	100,01
Italy	101,77	95,58	102,55	101,88	97,96	99,17	98,46	99,93	99,64
Jamaica	96,62	97,96	97,83	104,21	102,90	105,74	104,72	100,86	105,22
Japan	100,82	100,81	99,76	99,44	99,84	99,49	100,39	100,45	101,20
Jordan	88,31	92,57	101,40	106,03	97,04	103,90	98,06	101,87	102,78
Kazakhstan	93,28	94,62	99,13	106,25	111,29	113,81	110,37	117,05	114,69
Kenya	102,74	102,60	106,12	91,28	86,92	96,26	108,69	113,94	110,33
Kiribati	90,65	90,44	91,10	118,46	118,61	107,69	94,04	94,22	97,12
Korea, Dem. People's Rep.	104,78	103,24	98,49	98,27	95,17	92,57	102,59	94,54	92,34
Korea, Rep.	98,37	101,96	99,54	98,50	97,52	100,02	101,04	99,34	102,20
Kuwait	94,39	98,59	94,51	106,90	109,17	114,25	118,23	117,99	123,32
Kyrgyz Republic	92,09	93,38	102,28	104,34	105,66	107,41	109,48	110,33	104,94
Lao PDR	75,16	89,86	104,54	105,60	98,73	96,56	98,87	102,79	114,45
Latvia	84,64	88,75	107,21	104,04	106,11	83,55	104,75	110,86	101,52
Lebanon	89,13	95,09	98,71	106,20	107,16	105,44	100,66	99,70	100,05
Lesotho	105,99	106,67	100,76	92,56	114,06	107,04	89,33	90,94	100,35
Liberia	90,37	92,43	96,64	110,94	92,61	95,91	97,94	100,94	99,11
Libya	108,66	100,24	100,66	99,10	98,12	103,27	101,89	104,33	105,93
Lithuania	87,76	95,06	105,97	98,97	100,73	83,23	94,17	107,60	96,15
Luxembourg	91,92	96,69	102,08	101,23	104,67	111,03	110,39	113,61	112,69
Madagascar	97,64	101,11	98,81	100,08	97,39	100,53	100,60	102,47	103,76
Malawi	85,95	102,82	99,41	97,77	117,13	124,23	130,68	135,23	141,74
Malaysia	92,72	92,56	102,51	104,92	102,37	100,67	97,45	100,73	99,85
Maldives	95,15	98,34	99,67	101,99	101,50	100,68	104,66	105,61	93,86
Mali	90,94	89,03	98,09	112,88	113,15	123,80	127,61	136,85	126,32
Malta	101,50	104,36	99,30	96,34	95,03	80,80	73,71	77,73	76,43
Marshall Islands	116,67	83,33	90,00	126,67	126,67	80,00	90,04	90,04	95,42
Mauritania	94,88	98,29	100,31	101,40	103,34	107,07	104,40	105,94	111,75
Mauritius	100,33	102,64	100,23	97,13	97,57	89,19	94,19	80,40	83,23
Mexico	94,40	97,32	98,41	104,27	108,04	110,48	111,92	112,81	114,21
Micronesia, Fed. Sts.	85,23	100,05	99,45	100,51	101,04	101,12	101,31	101,55	101,91

Moldova	96,62	102,10	90,67	107,23	115,78	121,40	118,65	81,45	125,01
Mongolia	81,44	83,81	110,54	105,65	107,14	126,34	131,33	168,72	129,65
Montenegro	100,74	93,80	97,94	108,26	97,54	101,10	97,68	101,91	99,35
Morocco	98,53	100,05	108,10	91,86	108,46	115,69	110,16	98,63	115,66
Mozambique	105,63	102,81	97,36	99,83	114,81	133,88	135,03	135,75	139,77
Myanmar	98,23	97,97	101,00	101,03	101,62	80,24	79,94	79,83	78,43
Namibia	100,60	102,42	99,79	97,79	104,94	102,38	97,48	103,75	105,58
Nauru	104,71	99,27	99,96	100,76	99,49	100,11	100,57	101,11	101,83
Nepal	94,12	99,16	99,25	101,59	106,38	108,08	114,04	120,43	122,25
Netherlands	93,41	96,63	101,11	102,26	102,47	96,11	100,83	102,44	103,75
New Zealand	92,85	98,86	101,16	99,99	98,07	102,03	101,71	102,86	103,55
Nicaragua	98,81	98,49	97,16	104,35	114,81	114,25	115,37	120,00	123,81
Niger	84,43	90,15	101,51	108,34	110,84	119,81	118,78	129,37	113,88
Nigeria	85,31	96,24	98,50	105,26	107,27	111,74	107,48	106,28	108,05
North Macedonia	95,38	93,13	102,82	104,05	83,63	101,51	95,69	102,73	94,64
Norway	95,62	98,85	100,13	101,03	101,35	96,64	101,62	101,36	102,29
Oman	100,73	91,18	100,77	108,04	124,71	134,13	127,88	147,29	143,95
Pakistan	103,52	98,12	100,15	101,73	108,40	107,09	113,59	119,78	126,52
Panama	97,94	99,37	99,86	100,76	103,16	107,68	110,16	108,70	111,18
Papua New Guinea	94,62	99,49	99,81	100,70	101,24	102,71	102,51	102,58	103,43
Paraguay	92,89	99,60	98,81	101,59	110,54	110,22	102,31	117,12	110,43
Peru	94,45	98,08	98,97	102,96	102,85	110,94	115,72	118,02	122,48
Philippines	98,65	100,57	100,77	98,66	102,03	101,66	101,27	100,69	100,25
Poland	95,19	101,75	96,53	101,72	106,19	102,97	101,87	112,20	110,99
Portugal	94,28	93,67	107,53	98,80	110,24	101,90	111,67	107,92	127,77
Qatar	97,41	81,18	112,93	105,89	105,67	140,41	136,75	158,52	162,02
Romania	98,45	103,07	96,09	100,84	115,92	118,69	112,45	87,27	106,43
Russian Federation	92,60	97,58	100,04	102,38	107,41	104,68	109,98	111,93	111,47
Rwanda	131,36	97,98	100,64	101,38	114,22	108,34	122,72	124,95	129,24
Samoa	124,08	123,52	90,74	85,74	82,32	79,43	73,23	79,41	83,63
Sao Tome and Principe	110,50	106,36	89,31	104,33	110,89	106,54	105,53	103,68	104,42
Saudi Arabia	104,02	91,50	101,49	107,01	121,02	126,72	137,09	157,40	158,96
Senegal	80,94	84,28	110,06	105,65	132,78	152,97	152,20	181,33	177,74
Serbia	99,45	98,01	94,38	107,62	90,74	107,77	107,88	110,95	104,22
Seychelles	88,85	96,61	99,40	103,99	89,90	103,16	101,94	97,95	94,85
Sierra Leone	112,87	110,06	96,32	93,62	84,46	88,63	78,18	91,46	130,16
Singapore	96,50	95,25	99,27	105,48	133,20	112,51	123,76	123,62	112,25
Slovak Republic	93,54	104,73	89,58	105,69	91,88	97,90	97,94	101,26	97,38
Slovenia	91,08	97,67	101,74	100,59	97,55	102,60	99,91	105,00	97,41
Solomon Islands	98,49	99,84	100,59	99,58	100,37	101,26	100,05	100,68	102,23
Somalia	110,15	100,60	101,92	97,48	98,18	98,14	100,51	100,75	98,51
South Africa	97,40	102,95	100,99	96,06	105,85	104,32	104,54	111,39	114,31
South Sudan	94,40	98,56	100,64	100,80	100,15	101,95	107,01	105,07	113,01
Spain	104,22	94,50	99,39	106,11	101,65	117,74	106,66	117,57	116,91
Sri Lanka	99,17	89,76	105,56	104,68	83,18	105,00	107,94	125,88	130,31
St. Kitts and Nevis	101,97	100,99	99,72	99,29	95,34	97,24	97,08	95,22	98,50
St. Lucia	99,50	101,30	101,19	97,51	99,49	103,29	98,81	86,57	75,92

St. Vincent and the Grenadines	98,31	102,01	100,15	97,83	99,32	101,87	104,15	104,85	103,83
Sudan	94,64	103,31	91,73	104,96	101,73	117,60	114,97	115,54	113,66
Suriname	98,61	101,66	98,20	100,14	103,52	97,94	94,71	85,81	87,79
Sweden	93,26	99,57	102,35	98,08	100,96	84,16	100,78	101,18	96,49
Switzerland	97,37	102,58	99,43	97,98	97,74	101,65	97,32	99,03	95,33
Syrian Arab Republic	111,48	90,51	108,01	101,48	103,99	98,55	113,74	122,90	104,06
Tajikistan	78,72	79,52	111,67	108,81	119,36	131,70	138,70	135,94	128,77
Tanzania	93,36	98,98	103,49	97,53	99,07	107,75	108,47	112,31	113,67
Thailand	104,88	102,97	96,64	100,39	101,99	104,16	100,22	94,36	98,35
Timor-Leste	99,31	98,47	105,95	95,59	92,39	92,38	91,85	86,73	76,34
Togo	92,86	101,78	98,66	99,55	103,12	106,41	108,67	111,05	112,48
Tonga	127,38	95,21	106,32	98,46	98,56	96,91	96,98	96,90	94,39
Trinidad and Tobago	108,52	108,70	89,16	102,15	107,20	109,48	93,92	89,52	89,53
Tunisia	93,40	89,59	114,83	95,59	93,75	113,37	104,15	122,95	103,68
Turkiye	98,16	95,76	101,80	102,44	109,00	109,14	115,05	120,68	120,50
Turkmenistan	100,01	98,52	100,55	100,93	96,78	99,38	111,39	109,57	108,85
Tuvalu	99,64	98,81	100,21	100,97	101,93	102,00	112,48	112,90	108,96
Uganda	98,56	101,65	104,27	94,08	103,54	103,25	118,70	127,80	122,57
Ukraine	101,15	101,13	96,81	102,05	100,03	107,28	109,39	99,29	113,94
United Arab Emirates	78,77	94,36	98,36	107,28	107,31	111,43	114,48	118,28	124,71
United Kingdom	92,75	100,68	101,36	97,96	102,20	99,60	103,58	97,09	98,99
United States	95,81	98,13	97,01	104,86	101,96	103,20	99,65	104,05	105,46
Uruguay	96,27	102,76	101,26	95,99	104,32	88,76	101,50	91,82	98,83
Uzbekistan	86,92	93,08	100,51	106,41	101,18	105,11	105,23	106,96	109,94
Vanuatu	116,76	104,81	97,68	97,50	104,90	103,99	104,89	103,28	104,56
Venezuela, RB	104,53	105,75	101,45	92,79	88,83	82,03	82,12	86,85	85,78
Vietnam	95,90	98,67	100,73	100,60	101,67	105,31	104,83	106,07	111,65
Yemen, Rep.	108,53	108,13	99,62	92,25	91,56	90,93	104,33	108,21	104,92
Zambia	99,64	105,84	92,53	101,63	124,86	117,76	112,74	122,80	128,88
Zimbabwe	112,21	96,89	101,19	101,92	106,55	108,86	105,55	109,60	132,04

	ANN	PNN	Gradient Boosted Trees	Random Forest Regression
R^2	0,3863625135	-0,8339872351	0,6259907583	0,4268624674
<i>mean absolute error</i>	0,0973782221	0,2106742301	0,0896680919	0,0878033704
<i>mean squared error</i>	0,0151484188	0,0707537347	0,0135452975	0,0140706111
<i>root mean squared error</i>	0,1230789129	0,2659957420	0,1163842664	0,1186196068
	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression	Simple Regression Tree
R^2	0,5260815102	0,4753983278	0,6757363327	0,3303698851
<i>mean absolute error</i>	0,0786773439	0,1015790019	0,0728474657	0,1380356152
<i>mean squared error</i>	0,0148263499	0,0176423911	0,0111754027	0,0339173180
<i>root mean squared error</i>	0,1217634999	0,1328246629	0,1057137773	0,1841665496

	2021	Prediction	Var per
Afghanistan	0,415151238	0,373302717	-10,0803
Austria	0,287763867	0,317786888	10,43321
Azerbaijan	0,536141826	0,460946672	-14,0252
Bahrain	0,548752627	0,694685196	26,59351
Bangladesh	0,439367632	0,402538988	-8,38219

Belarus	0,317006305	0,342087276	7,911821
Bolivia	0,441012519	0,386631945	-12,3308
Bosnia and Herzegovina	0,248834872	0,41799522	67,98097
Brunei Darussalam	0,442017728	0,366124206	-17,1698
Canada	0,252581559	0,407567655	61,36081
Chad	0,497943891	0,473958947	-4,8168
Comoros	0,342776204	0,363350338	6,002206
Croatia	0,126382162	0,336173763	165,9978
Djibouti	0,692863017	0,756664632	9,208402
Ecuador	0,327149776	0,294870886	-9,8667
Gambia, The	0,038289317	0,092053484	140,4156
Georgia	0,44941972	0,464463437	3,347365
Greece	0,243808828	0,290338894	19,08465
Grenada	0,238600018	0,246269539	3,214384
Guatemala	0,333455177	0,355063801	6,480218
Iran, Islamic Rep.	0,141368912	0,18423222	30,32018
Italy	0,286301745	0,289062369	0,964236
Kazakhstan	0,423832587	0,451057369	6,423475
Korea, Dem. People's Rep.	0,219592434	0,263427789	19,96214
Lesotho	0,292789911	0,326352384	11,46299
Malaysia	0,28822078	0,284233507	-1,38341
Maldives	0,233482592	0,333467767	42,8234
Mauritania	0,396966097	0,366457092	-7,68554
Micronesia, Fed. Sts.	0,3070456	0,338401951	10,21228
Mozambique	0,653020196	0,69705293	6,742936
New Zealand	0,322032349	0,326280714	1,319235
Pakistan	0,531938225	0,441992837	-16,909
Papua New Guinea	0,320935758	0,329937116	2,804723
Paraguay	0,384903591	0,448857758	16,61563
Peru	0,495019647	0,437132292	-11,694
Philippines	0,291876085	0,319169037	9,35087
Portugal	0,543361053	0,327415063	-39,7426
Qatar	0,856346523	0,575007952	-32,8534
Russian Federation	0,394407384	0,386564863	-1,98843
Rwanda	0,556794298	0,696710532	25,12889
Sao Tome and Principe	0,329982637	0,376435449	14,07735
Saudi Arabia	0,828383441	0,631490954	-23,7683
Senegal	1	0,84837999	-15,162
Solomon Islands	0,309969844	0,313345801	1,089124
Spain	0,444119528	0,477824528	7,589173
St. Kitts and Nevis	0,275884127	0,274017877	-0,67646
St. Lucia	0,069542173	0,237740101	241,8646
Sweden	0,25751622	0,264482397	2,705141
Thailand	0,274513388	0,30492991	11,08016
Tonga	0,23832587	0,433528	81,90556
Tunisia	0,323220323	0,375456374	16,16113
Uganda	0,495842091	0,440933481	-11,0738

United Arab Emirates	0,515397971	0,486568992	-5,59354
Uzbekistan	0,380425843	0,352668518	-7,29638
Vanuatu	0,331261994	0,428484179	29,34903
Yemen, Rep.	0,334551768	0,35347307	5,655717
Zambia	0,553504523	0,545569423	-1,43361

	R^2	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Sum
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>Gradient Boosted Trees</i>	2	4	2	2	10
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	3	2	4	4	13
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	4	3	3	3	14
<i>ANN</i>	5	5	5	5	21
<i>Linear Regression</i>	6	6	6	6	22
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	7	7	7	7	28
<i>PNN</i>	8	8	8	8	32